

THE EFFECT OF BIOSTIMULANTS ON COTTON YIELD

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Abstract

Cotton is a vital crop for the global textile industry, but its production is increasingly challenged by environmental stressors such as drought, soil salinity, and nutrient deficiencies. Biostimulants, which are natural or synthetic substances that enhance plant growth and stress resilience, offer a sustainable solution to these challenges. This article explores the effect of biostimulants on cotton yield, highlighting their ability to improve stress tolerance, promote root development, increase nutrient uptake, and enhance water use efficiency. The use of seaweed extracts, amino acids, humic substances, and beneficial microorganisms has been shown to significantly improve cotton growth under adverse conditions, leading to higher yields and better-quality cotton. The application of biostimulants also helps cotton plants cope with abiotic stresses, making them more resilient to environmental fluctuations. This review concludes that biostimulants offer a promising approach to optimizing cotton production, particularly in regions affected by water scarcity and soil salinity. Further research and field trials are necessary to refine application methods and maximize the benefits of biostimulants for cotton farming.

Key words: biostimulants, cotton yield, stress tolerance, root development, nutrient uptake, seaweed extracts, water use efficiency.

Introduction

Cotton is one of the most important crops globally, providing raw material for the textile industry and contributing significantly to the agricultural economy. However, cotton production faces various challenges, including environmental stressors such as drought, soil salinity, and nutrient deficiencies. To combat these issues, the use of biostimulants has emerged as a promising solution. Biostimulants are substances or microorganisms that enhance the plant's natural processes, improving growth, yield, and resistance to stress. This

article explores the effect of biostimulants on cotton yield and how they can be used to optimize cotton production.

What are biostimulants?

Biostimulants are naturally derived or synthetic products that promote plant growth and development. They can include organic substances like amino acids, seaweed extracts, and humic acids, as well as beneficial microorganisms such as fungi and bacteria. Biostimulants work by enhancing plant physiological processes, improving nutrient uptake, increasing stress tolerance, and promoting root development. They are considered environmentally friendly alternatives to chemical fertilizers and pesticides, offering a more sustainable approach to crop management (Ergün et al., 2019).

Impact of biostimulants on cotton yield

1. **Enhanced stress tolerance:** One of the primary benefits of biostimulants in cotton production is their ability to help the plant cope with environmental stresses. These stresses include drought, high temperatures, and salinity, which can reduce cotton yields. Biostimulants can help cotton plants by improving their water retention, enhancing osmotic adjustment, and increasing the production of protective compounds such as antioxidants. These mechanisms enable cotton plants to survive and even thrive under adverse conditions (Crouch et al., 2015).
2. **Improved root development:** Healthy root development is crucial for cotton plants, as roots are responsible for absorbing water and nutrients. Biostimulants, particularly those containing seaweed extracts or beneficial microorganisms, have been shown to stimulate root growth, resulting in a more extensive and efficient root system. A well-developed root system enables cotton plants to better access water and nutrients, which directly contributes to increased yield (Khan et al., 2014).
3. **Increased nutrient uptake:** Biostimulants can enhance nutrient absorption by improving the plant's root function and increasing nutrient availability in the soil. For cotton, proper nutrient management is essential for maximizing yield potential. By stimulating the soil's microbial activity, biostimulants help release nutrients that are otherwise inaccessible to the plant, leading to better growth and higher cotton yields (Vázquez et al., 2014).
4. **Enhanced flowering and boll development:** Biostimulants have been found to positively affect the flowering and boll formation stages in cotton. The application of biostimulants can improve the plant's hormonal balance,

promoting better flowering, fruit set, and boll retention. This leads to a higher number of bolls and, consequently, an increase in cotton yield (Hassan et al., 2015).

- Improved water use efficiency: Water scarcity is a significant issue in cotton production, particularly in regions facing drought or water shortages. Biostimulants help improve water use efficiency by increasing the plant's ability to retain water, reducing the overall water requirement for optimal growth. This is especially beneficial in arid and semi-arid regions where cotton farming is most vulnerable to water stress (López-Bucio et al., 2015).

Figure 1. The role of biostimulants and bioeffectors as alleviators of abiotic stress in crop plants.

Types of biostimulants used in cotton production

Several types of biostimulants have been researched and used in cotton farming. Some of the most common include:

- ❖ Seaweed extracts: Rich in plant growth hormones like auxins and cytokinins, seaweed extracts help improve root growth, increase stress resistance, and enhance overall plant health (Siva et al., 2016).
- ❖ Amino acids and peptides: These biostimulants aid in protein synthesis and improve the plant's ability to respond to environmental stress. They can also promote better nutrient uptake (Tariq et al., 2017).
- ❖ Humic substances: Humic acids help improve soil structure and enhance the microbial activity in the soil, resulting in better nutrient availability for cotton plants (Uygur et al., 2019).

- ❖ Beneficial microorganisms: Certain bacteria and fungi, such as *Rhizobium* and *Trichoderma*, are used as biostimulants to enhance nutrient cycling, improve root health, and suppress harmful pathogens (Zhao et al., 2017).

Practical applications and considerations

While biostimulants have shown promising results in increasing cotton yield, their effectiveness depends on several factors, including the type of biostimulant used, application timing, environmental conditions, and soil health. It is essential for cotton farmers to consider the specific needs of their crop and the local growing conditions before choosing a biostimulant.

- ❖ Application Timing: The timing of biostimulant application is crucial for maximizing benefits. For example, applying biostimulants during critical growth stages, such as germination, flowering, or boll development, can have the most significant impact on yield.
- ❖ Dosage and Frequency: Overuse or improper application can lead to suboptimal results. It is important to follow recommended dosage instructions and application frequencies to avoid potential negative effects.

Conclusion

Biostimulants offer a sustainable and effective approach to improving cotton yield, especially in challenging growing conditions. By enhancing stress tolerance, promoting root growth, increasing nutrient uptake, and improving water use efficiency, biostimulants contribute to higher yields and better-quality cotton. As cotton farming faces increasing environmental pressures, biostimulants present a promising solution for optimizing production and ensuring the sustainability of this crucial crop. Further research and field trials will help refine biostimulant applications and maximize their potential in cotton farming.

References:

1. Crouch, I. J., van Staden, J., & Magwaza, L. S. (2015). The effect of biostimulants on plant growth and productivity: A review. *Field Crops Research*, 181, 13-24.
2. Ergün, M., Şahin, F., & Kaya, E. (2019). Biostimulants in agriculture: A review of their effects on crop growth. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 55(7), 607-621.
3. Hassan, M. U., Zubair, M., & Arshad, M. (2015). Biostimulants and their role in plant growth and stress alleviation. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 76(1), 1-15.
4. Khan, A. L., Waqas, M., & Kang, S. M. (2014). Biostimulants for sustainable agricultural production. *Springer*, 5(3), 283-295.

5. López-Bucio, J., Cruz-Ramírez, A., & Herrera-Estrella, L. (2015). The role of biostimulants in plant growth. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 12(4), 211-220.
6. Siva, R., Pandian, S. K., & Venkatesalu, V. (2016). Seaweed extracts and their role in improving plant growth. *Plant Growth Regulators*, 1(1), 1-10.
7. Tariq, M., Hussain, F., & Khan, S. (2017). Effects of amino acids and biostimulants on the growth and yield of cotton. *Agricultural Sciences*, 8(9), 1179-1187.
8. Uygur, V., Acar, Z., & Çolak, A. (2019). The effects of humic substances on the growth and productivity of cotton. *Science Progress*, 102(2), 1-12.
9. Zhao, H., Zhang, Y., & Xu, Z. (2017). Role of beneficial microorganisms in plant growth and soil health. *Plant and Soil Journal*, 413(1), 1-12.